

CBCS

ASSAY DEVELOPMENT GUIDELINE

Important steps in creating a successful assay

CBCS v2024.1

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1. Introduction

Unique assays developed in relevant biological environments are the first step toward investigating small molecules. At CBCS, we provide collaborative and supportive services to design and enhance robust assays that meet specific research needs. Whether it involves creating accurate biochemical assays or utilizing sophisticated cell-based models, CBCS offers the necessary tools for successful hit identification. Specializing in adapting bioassays for high-throughput applications, we assist assay transfer from laboratory settings to microtiter-based formats and enable robust screening in 96-, 384-, and 1536-well plates using automation.

This document provides stepwise guidelines of assay development process, which includes crucial and practical information for setting up an assay toward high throughput screening (HTS) applications. Tips and tricks are summarized from our experience in creating successful HTS assays.

Critical steps in the assay development process:

We use the [Assay Guidance Manual | National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences\(nih.gov\)](#) as a general reference), and selected chapters are referred to in the end for specific topics mentioned in this guideline.

If you are considering collaborating with us and using our services, please contact CBCS scientists about your research plan as early as possible. We provide consultation on the technical feasibility of assays and can help with pilot assay development experiments in preparation for large project support. See <https://www.cbcs.se/> for more information about our services and mechanism for collaboration.

2. Assay Design

At this stage, assay technology and detection methods should be decided. There are commercial kits and reagents suitable for different assay types (target-based or phenotypic; using isolated-protein, cells) and different target types (enzyme, protein-protein interaction, transmembrane receptor, transcription factor etc..).

If some assay components need to be customized for your specific need, we highly recommend talking to CBCS scientists to discuss options or alternatives.

2.1 General recommendations for assay design

Considerations		Tips and Tricks
ASSAY DESIGN	Detection method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fluorescence or luminescence > absorbance ○ Glow-type > flash-type for luminescence ○ Red-shifted dyes are preferred to prevent compound interference ○ Change in ionic current
	Workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Minimize assay steps: Avoid sample transfer as much as possible and use addition-only procedures. ○ Use end-point readouts for HTS, but kinetics should be measured during assay optimization.
	Materials	<p style="text-align: center;">Cell-based assays</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ All cell lines should pass STR verification and mycoplasma testing. ○ Ensure enough cells from the same frozen batch for all experiments. ○ Stable cell lines are highly preferred over transient transfected cells. ○ If the expressed protein is toxic for the cell, inducible expression is recommended. ○ If transient transfection is necessary, all plasmids should be sequenced to confirm their identity. ○ If transient transfection is necessary, the transfection efficiency should be robust, as high as possible and reproducible. <p>Biochemical assays</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ensure high-quality protein and substrates are in sufficient amounts. ○ If possible, perform preliminary activity tests on the assay materials. ○ Ideally, the same batch of materials should be used for consistency.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In case of limited protein expression, a reduced culturing temperature (27-30 °C) is recommended for 1-3 days prior to recordings. ○ Ensure valid ethical permits for primary cell lines.
Cost		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Estimate how much assay materials will be needed and calculate the total cost for the screen and plan the scale of the screen accordingly.

3. Assay optimization

The goal of this step is to determine an optimal assay procedure and condition in preparation for a scale-up screen. Important assay parameters to be considered in the optimization step include signal intensity, assay window and variability. Notably, an optimal assay condition is not always selected based on the highest signal; more often, it is a compromised decision that balances multiple assay parameters with other practical factors such as workflow, time, and cost.

3.1 Considerations for biochemical/isolated protein-based assays

		Typical steps	Tips and Tricks
ASSAY OPTIMIZATION	Materials	a. Optimize concentrations of the target protein, substrate/cofactor and detecting reagents. ¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Excessive substrate depletion will result in a loss of assay sensitivity. When the aim is to find inhibitors, it is important to stay below 50% substrate conversion. Saturation of the detection reagents and readers can also result in low assay sensitivity. Measure signal linearity and determine K_m or K_d is recommended. When the aim is to find competitive inhibitors, it is wise to choose a substrate/ligand concentration at or below K_m/K_d and make sure $[S/L] \gg [Target]$. Cross-titration experiments can be conducted to identify the best concentration pair of two reagents
		b. Evaluate reagent stability at different temperatures and over time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Run time-course experiments at 37°C, in RT and on ice. Conduct freeze/thaw cycle experiments
	Assay buffer	c. Optimize buffer components, such as pH, types of salts, reducing agents, detergents and blocking reagents.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detergents and blocking reagents (fish gelatin, BSA etc.) help prevent aggregation in protein and compounds and reduce non-specific binding to the plastics. Optimize one component at a time, with the most relevant component first. Optimize the osmolarity of intra- and extracellular solutions to minimize drifts in current over time.
		d. Optimize concentrations of the other components, if they are related to the activity and stability of the target protein.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concentration of salts and pH can affect protein stability by changing electrostatic of the protein surface. Reducing agent protects the protein from oxidization. Metal ions can be essential for protein activity. E.g. Mg^{2+} activates kinases, while Ca^{2+} and Zn^{2+} are required for other proteins.

ASSAY OPTIMIZATION			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigate if seal enhancers are required for a high membrane resistance. Lack of seal enhancers is preferred.
		e. Test DMSO tolerance (0-2%) of the assay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The library compounds are stored in DMSO. DMSO tolerance data is required to define a proper assay volume and compound concentration for the screen.
	Workflow	f. Optimize the sequence of adding reagents and incubation time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adding reagents to dozens of 384- or 1536-well plates and obtaining signals of each on a plate reader well will take time. The logistics of adding and reading is especially critical when the reagents are unstable, or the assay readout is time sensitive. Test the workflow with dummy plates can help estimate the processing time and arrange proper batch size
		g. Perform a time-course experiment and obtain a full kinetic curve. Define an optimal endpoint as the HTS readout.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time curves can indicate assay robustness and reagent stability. Choose a time point in the linear range that gives a good enough signal and is adaptable for HTS.
	Instrument and automation	h. Reader: optimize measurement settings, adjust mirror and filters, time of reading, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A shortcut is to use existing protocols for the same assay technology and modify from there. Different plate types (colour, material, and coating) can have a great impact on the assay response.² Test a few plate types and choose the best for your assay. Sometimes a plate calibration is required to reduce plate variability. Optimize the voltage range and duration to be included in the experiments.
		i. Liquid handler: optimize volume and speed of dispensing; if a washing step is included, optimize volume and times of washing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Same as the manual pipettes, standard cassettes (5 μL and up) and small cassettes (1 μL and up) have different working volumes, choose wisely to reduce assay variations. Test with dummy plates on liquid handlers, looking for dispensing consistency in the wells, the likelihood of generating air bubbles, and any clogged cassette tips. Perform cleaning and calibration if necessary. The mechanical forces of instruments can cause damage to the assay materials. Reduce dispensing and aspiration speed and minimize the number of washes if the materials are sensitive. Consider washing with dissolvent if risk of compound cross-contamination between applications.

		j. Centrifuge and shaker	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Centrifuge after each adding step to mix reagents and remove bubbles, except after dispensing cells.○ Shaking is usually required during incubation when using beads/resin for keeping a homogeneous mixture
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Concepts of K_m and K_d , the use of reaction time course and linearity relating to an enzymatic assay are well explained in the reference article.¹

There might be additional considerations relating to specific target and assay technologies. Representative biochemical assay examples are described in the Assay Guidance Manual.³

3.2 Considerations for cell-based assays

		Typical steps	Tips and Tricks
ASSAY OPTIMIZATION	Cells and reagents	a. Verify the cells and expression of your target gene/protein. Save enough frozen cells from the 'good' batch.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Consistency is key. Keep track of the splitting and use the same or close generations in different experimental batches. ○ Perform a quality control test on newly thawed cells before starting the large-scale screen ○ Avoid too newly thawed and cells at too high passage numbers for recordings.
		b. Optimize cell seeding density and reagent concentration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Avoid depletion of reagents, saturation on the reader, or over-growth of cells for imaging ○ Can measure a few time points ○ For electrophysiology: Avoid using completely confluent cells since this may cause a stop of protein expression and result in bad quality of the recording. ○ For electrophysiology: Cell viability should be very high, (>97% measured by trypan blue exclusion) ○ For electrophysiology: Cell detachment is crucial, cells need to be single-cell suspension but with minimal enzyme treatment and mechanical force
	Culture media /assay buffer	c. Optimize media components, such +/- phenol red, increase or decrease concentrations of serum/antibiotics/selecting reagent.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Some assays might suffer from interference from phenol red in cell culture media, and it is advised to test the assay without it. ○ FBS and other chemicals sometimes may interfere with the assay. Use without or at reduced concentration if it happens.
		d. DMSO tolerance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The library compounds are stored in DMSO. Cell-based assays can be very sensitive and generally don't exceed 0.5% DMSO in the final solution for compound treatment.
Workflow, Instrument, and Automation:			
refer to the previous table on biochemical/isolated protein-based assays			

There might be additional considerations relating to specific cell types and assay technologies. Representative cell-based assay examples are described in the Assay Guidance Manual.⁴

Notably, assay development guidelines for high-content image-based screening assays are described.^{5,6}

3.3 Other recommendations

We recommend **performing experiments using a positive and negative control** if they are available. The controls should generate the maximum and minimum assay signals that represent the assay window, and they are essential to evaluate assay variability. If such compounds are not available, alternative approaches to obtain maximum and minimum assay signals should be used.

It is also important to **consider compound interferences** with the assay readout and how to circumvent this. Various mechanisms of compound interference in assays are described.⁷ As a follow-up, a counter-screen should be performed to address this or conduct experiments to identify compounds that interfere with the assay readout or act through an unwanted mechanism. This could include checking for compounds that absorb or are fluorescent at the used wavelength, and compounds that might be redox active, reactive, or aggregators. For cell-based assays, this could include checking if the compounds are toxic to the cells or act through non-specific mechanisms like phospholipidosis.

Lastly, it is recommended to **perform a pre-screen** with a subset of compound plates to check that the assay is truly robust and reproducible and that the assay workflow works as expected.

CBCS has a set of compounds called 'assay optimization kit', which contains 4 compound pre-screen plates (diverse commercial screening compounds), two dirty plates (autofluorescence, metal chelators, redox compounds etc.) and 2 plates with DMSO, in 384-well format. This kit is designed for conducting pre-screening and identifying potential assay interferences.

1536-well plate:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48						
A	0	0	POS	POS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	DMSC	DMSC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
B	0	0	POS	POS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	DMSC	DMSC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
C	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
D	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	POS	POS	DMSC	DMSC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	POS	POS	DMSC	DMSC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
F	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
G	DMSC	DMSC	0	0	0	0	POS	POS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
H	DMSC	DMSC	0	0	0	0	POS	POS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
I	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	DMSC	DMSC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
J	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	DMSC	DMSC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
K	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
L	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
M	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
N	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
O	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Q	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
R	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
S	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
T	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
U	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
V	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
W	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
X	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Y	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Z	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
AA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
AB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
AC	POS	POS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
AD	POS	POS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
AE	DMSC	DMSC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
AF	DMSC	DMSC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

5. Assay validation and statistics.

Assay validation aims to verify that the assay is robust and reproducible.⁸ An important measurement is the statistical analysis of the assay results, namely assay quality control (QC). Z' factor is used to evaluate assay quality.⁹ It is a determinant assessing the separation band between the positive control data set and the negative control data set and calculates using the following equation:

$$Z' = 1 - \frac{3SD \text{ of pos. control} + 3SD \text{ of neg. control}}{[\text{mean of pos. control} - \text{mean of neg. control}]}$$

Z' reflects the magnitude of the separation band. A large separation band indicates that a positive signal is readily distinguished from a negative signal (see figure below). It indicates high confidence of a positive hit in a screen to be distinguished from a substance with no effect. An assay with good separation between negative and positive controls should have a **Z' factor > 0.5**.

Perform several QC experiments to assess the variability within and between plates, and from day to day to confirm assay reproducibility.

You also need to pay attention to the **plate edge effect**. It can be caused by various circumstances, such as exposure to temperature gradient during the assay reaction, evaporation during incubation, or imprecise dispensing of the liquid handling equipment. In most cases it can be avoided with a few tricks¹⁰:

- Test the liquid handling equipment with dummy plates and coloured solutions to observe the evenness of dispensing and to identify potential clogging. Thoroughly clean and calibrate the instrument if necessary.
- For target-based assays, running the reaction at room temperature is recommended. If possible, use room-tempered reagents and seal the assay plates or place them in a humidity box during the incubation. The lid can be put tightly on the box for target-based assays to prevent evaporation.
- For cell-based assays, after dispensing, let the cells settle and adhere to the plate for 10-15 minutes before incubation. A humidity box can be created by adding wet paper tissues to the bottom of a plastic box and placing the plates on the box during incubation to prevent evaporation. The lid should only be loosely put on top of the box for appropriate CO₂.

Lastly, **validate assay sensitivity with known reference compounds**. If available, use your assay to obtain EC₅₀ or IC₅₀ of known agonists, inhibitors, or modulators and compare results with the literature data. If you have several reference compounds with varying potencies, the dynamic range of your assay can also be assessed.

6. References

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7. My notes and action points